

PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF EDUCATIONAL WORK IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Norbayeva Mokhigul Shavkatovna

Teacher of the Faculty of "Pedagogy and Psychology" of Alfraganus University

Annotation: In this article, on the basis of the analysis of the specific features of the processes of educational relations organized in educational institutions, to increase the effectiveness of the methodology of educational work in general secondary educational institutions, to meaningfully organize the free time of students outside of the classroom and outside of school, first of all to create a perfect person, the features of the manifestation of the content of education science in students is demonstrated.

Key words: higher education institutions, educational work, form, style, harmony of the theory with practice, teaching methodology.

The most effective way to educate the student community in the organization and management of educational work processes in higher education institutions is to set requirements and set goals based on the individual interests of students. Demands are only effective when they are actionable:

- Pedagogical requirements for students should be based on the individual characteristics of each team member, and an environment of mutual respect should be formed. This is an important part of pedagogical etiquette, which ensures the effectiveness of goal-oriented activities. they are given special trust and respect.
- The team of future pedagogues should study the requirements in relation to their work, and set them taking into account the specific conditions of a particular group. Students should work towards their goals in the harmony of theory and practice. Every year, when they start working in school institutions, it is appropriate to form skills about what requirements to make to students in a certain quarter, half-year or during the academic year. Students should practice the skills of passing education in this way.
- Students should be clear about the requirements they use during practice and take into account the possibilities of completing the task. Students should clearly understand what is required of students. It consists in introducing students to the content of the requirements and regularly monitoring their implementation. Implementation of purposeful activities in educating the student body is of great

importance. If the group of students does not have a clear goal, it will not be possible to develop their scientific potential, outlook, and knowledge. There are the following ways to achieve the goal:

1. The teacher himself puts the main pedagogical requirement before the students. In this case, the combination of practical and theoretical knowledge gives students an understanding of its effectiveness. Shows ways to achieve the goal and tries to interest team members;
2. Team members promote interesting intellectual games, the use of various methods, the team leader supports this initiative, and provides practical support for implementation.

The first method is set at the initial stage of forming a team of students - it is called a goal for the near future. The second is a mid-term goal set by group activists at a much higher level. If all members of the team set the set goals, this is called a long-term goal and means that the team members are formed. As the student body grows and strengthens, medium and long-term goals are set for the team.

For example: contracts for internships, development of various methods for schools, study together with play activities for primary and secondary classes in extracurricular time, involvement in sports activities. Making future plans to spend the vacation time meaningfully, etc.

In order for the team to always move forward in its activities, it is necessary to set a new, interesting goal in front of it. It will be difficult to achieve the goal if the team does not have enthusiasm and enthusiasm. Oriental education plays an important role in the formation of the student community. Nothing can strengthen the student body like an oriental nursery school. The formation of oriental education and its preservation is an important task of education. It has become a tradition in the Asian countries to carry out oriental education and modern education in harmony. After all, the children of our nation are highly spiritual. Existing traditions can be conditionally divided into two groups:

- A) daily life traditions,
- B) holiday traditions.

Daily life traditions are various types of mutual support of students during their educational activities in a collective environment, cleaning classrooms together, spending Saturdays, taking care of animals together in the lively corner of the school, school including taking care of plants in the yard, receiving messages from lonely seniors on holidays, and more.

Holiday traditions include the national holidays of the Uzbek people, Navruz, Independence Day, Kurban Hayit, etc. In any case, it is necessary to organize the holidays in a colorful, bright, interesting, cheerful, festive manner, which is suitable for the interests of the students. The main goal is for the students to understand the moral content of the event, its place in their intellectual potential, and to have a conscious attitude towards them. At the stages of development of the student body, each Higher Education Institution has its own traditions. These new traditions will be connected with the educational activities carried out in this higher education institution, they will enliven and decorate the life of students. Therefore, students are given great opportunities to actively participate in the origin of the new tradition.

In higher education institutions, pedagogues should not impose or forcibly inculcate this or that extra tradition on the student body. Their task is to teach the student community the concept of creating traditions, to work together in the preparation and implementation of traditions, and to teach students to continue these traditions. It is always necessary to introduce innovations to the tradition that reflect new pedagogical requirements and increase its educational value. Traditions increase from year to year and gradually ensure the uniqueness of OTM. Thus, perspectives and traditions related to learning activities are important at all levels of community development. Based on the above, it is possible to indicate the following as the main factors of educating young people in a team spirit:

- using the methodology of "setting an example" to give examples from the work experience of the most advanced enterprise teams, from the lives of families and parents that are exemplary in harmony, solidarity, team and comradely mutual assistance;
- to explain, on the basis of comprehensive examples, how people should be a community in their lives, live in a friendly brotherly relationship with each other, work and create, and open a great way for their lives and marriages to always be beautiful and happy . On the contrary, to explain that if people live their lives without properly assessing the community and its requirements, they will end up without marriage and without spiritual wealth. Philosophically and pedagogically, he interprets these characteristics and principles of the community in a wide and deep way.

Community and individual relationships are important in our social life. A person's personality is related to his relations with other people, society, homeland, and all opportunities. So, a person is a biological concept, a personal social concept.

Condemning the natural needs of people and turning them into social mechanisms, politicization of nature, and ideological oppression leads to the devaluing of people. The general interest of the team and the personal interest of the students are combined and harmonized. And in this case, students understand that the goal and interest of the team is more important than personal interest, that each student should think about the students in the whole group, and that the whole team should think and care about each student in this team. It is of great importance in the socialization of students. earns. The important thing is that a friendly atmosphere is created in the team. Under the influence of such an environment, students realize that life without teenage friends is very boring and meaningless. Therefore, it is appropriate for the leader of each group to explain to his students what ways and means can be used to form a team, and its essence. It is important to use aphorisms about public and friendly mutual assistance, read books, give examples from events, and educate students in the public spirit. Students can effectively fight for its implementation only if they thoroughly understand the nature of the community. It is necessary to convincingly and effectively teach students that the community is the main tool for the development of the community and the individual in the process of education. The problem of the community and the individual is considered one of the most urgent theoretical and practical issues of educating the young generation. From this point of view, it is the task of general secondary education institutions to accustom students to public spirit, community life, to organize as a team, to create skills, and to form public consciousness. A person should not only be fully developed, but he should be socially active, use all his strength and capabilities to serve the Motherland, and find his place in society. In addition, a person's personal capabilities, skills and abilities are effectively used in serving the Motherland. One of the main features of the community is the formation of patriotism in students. Because the feeling of patriotism is caring for one's motherland and destiny. True patriots fight for their motherland, prosperity and freedom of their people. Students learn about mutual assistance between people, communities, and countries and understand their meaning. It is an excellent resource for educating people, students, in reading letters and in mutual relations, the feeling of sharing and helping each other. In addition, the next form of peer support is the permanent attachment of students who are good students to students who are not good students. At such a time, the method of working with a group comes in handy. Another form of friendly mutual support is manifested in the preparation of lessons in small groups. Friendly mutual support is seen in art lovers, preparing students for sports

competitions, and helping them in the work of leaders. Friendly mutual support is a way to actively participate students in Saturday and Sunday classes. Efforts to have a conscious attitude to work, organization of Saturdays and Sundays in our country are especially important. It should be said that it is the main source of education of public feeling in the community - students. Any team, no matter how it is, no matter what specific task is set before it, must use it as a source of education for students. The student community serves as a source of one or another component and qualities of students' education. Thus, the fact that the team is the source of educating students' sense of community can be clearly seen in the fact that students participate in social and useful activities as a team, go on trips as a team, participate in summer labor and recreation camps, various competitions and auditions. . As students take part in these events, moral qualities such as working together for the common good, caring for the common good and putting the common good above personal benefit, mutual help, cooperation, unity, and harmony are formed. In some cases, some students may develop negative moral manifestations, such as individualism and selfishness, which are against the public. In our opinion, it is necessary to take into account such cases when determining that the community is a source of education in students' sense of community. So, public education is intended to inculcate in the minds of students to be a joint team, to work for the benefit of the majority, to subordinate personal interest to the common good, and to help each other impartially and as comrades. Special attention is paid to engaging students in socially useful work, team work, work and cultural recreation. In higher education institutions, students are taught that the basis of work is pleasure, that work, and only work, can make all of a person's dreams come true. We pay special attention to the appreciation of any kind of work in teaching students to work and having the right attitude towards work. Hashar has its historical and social roots. In the past, as a result of hard work, the poor farmers were alone and did not have the opportunity to work the land allotted to them.

Hashar in its essence is team work, and it can be called team work dedicated by the team for the benefit of a certain person. Because in this way, a certain person, on the one hand, will benefit materially, and on the other hand, he will be enriched spiritually. It is characteristic that the students' visit to the festival creates a good mood in them. Therefore, it is not difficult to notice that hashar brings joy and pleasure to students. Through Hashar, students' parents, school administration, student body, group team and, in general, feel that they have fulfilled their duties as students in front of the public. At the same time, students feel more refreshed, energetic and loyal by meeting

people's needs by participating in the hashar. By participating in the festival, students realize that serving the common good and pursuing higher goals is the primary duty of people. Finally, by participating in the hashar, students will increasingly form community-specific qualities such as close contact, making friends, helping each other, solidarity, unity, and self-sacrifice. Therefore, hashar is one of the main means of educating students in public spirit. Along with the teaching process, the importance of work outside the auditorium is extremely important in educating students in a team spirit.

REFERENCES:

. 144 bet.

urg'unov S.T. Boshqaruv jarayonida tarbiyaviy munosabatlar/ maktab va hoyot jurnali 2006.20-23 betlar. B.Normurodova. Matnazarova K. Rahmonqulova Tarbiyaviy ishlar metodikasi. O'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent, "Fan" 2008 y.

3. Axmadaliyev B.S. Farmonov O.N. tarbiyaviy ishlar metodikasi. O'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent- 2022y

4. Djurayeva S.N. Turdiyeva N.S. Baxronova A.I. Tarbiyaviy ishlar metodikasi. O'quv qo'llanma. 11-23 bet.

5. Ishmuxammedov R, Abduqodirov A, Pardayev A, Tarbiyada ishlatiladigan texnologiyalar (o'quv qo'llanma) – T 2010yil.

6. www.pedagog.uz

7. www.edu.uz

8. www.gov.uz

9. www.ziyonet.uz